

Appendix_C1: Keyword-Driven Search Strategy

A systematic and keyword-driven search strategy was employed to ensure comprehensive coverage of relevant literature in databases and academic repositories. The strategy involved identifying key terms and phrases aligned with the study's objectives, as well as utilizing Boolean operators and database filters to refine search results.

Keywords and Key Phrases
<p>1) <i>Primary Keywords:</i></p> <p>"Spatial teaching"</p> <p>"Spatial reasoning"</p> <p>"Spatial ability development"</p> <p>"Spatial learning strategies"</p> <p>2) <i>Barriers and Enablers:</i></p> <p>"Barriers to teaching spatial skills"</p> <p>"Challenges in spatial education"</p> <p>"Enablers of spatial reasoning"</p> <p>"Facilitators of spatial skill development"</p> <p>3) <i>Education Contexts:</i></p> <p>"Primary education"</p> <p>"Elementary school teaching"</p> <p>"STEM education in primary schools"</p> <p>4) <i>Professional Development and Pedagogy:</i></p> <p>"Teacher training in spatial skills"</p> <p>"Professional development for spatial teaching"</p> <p>"Pedagogical interventions for spatial ability"</p>
Search Databases and Platforms
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ERIC (Education Resources Information Center)• PsycINFO• Scopus• Google Scholar• Education Source (EBSCOhost)• Web of Science

Boolean Operators and Search Modifiers

- **AND:** To combine different concepts and ensure all aspects are covered.
Example: "Spatial teaching" AND "barriers" AND "primary education"
- **OR:** To expand the search by including synonyms or related terms.
Example: "Spatial ability development" OR "spatial reasoning skills"
- **NOT:** To exclude irrelevant terms and focus on primary education.
Example: "Spatial teaching" NOT "secondary education"
- **Wildcards and Truncation:**
Example: "spatial*" to capture "spatial reasoning," "spatial learning," etc.

Search Process

- **Initial Broad Search:**
A broad search using general keywords to gather a wide range of articles.
- **Filtering and Refinement:**
Applied filters for publication date, peer-reviewed sources, and English language.
- **Review of Titles and Abstracts:**
Screened titles and abstracts to identify studies that met inclusion criteria.
- **Full-Text Analysis:**
Retrieved and reviewed full texts for relevance and alignment with the study objectives.
- **Backward and Forward Citation Tracking:**
Analyzed reference lists and citations within key articles to identify additional relevant studies.